

DEVELOPMENT OF A QUALITY AIR SENSOR: AIRGUARD

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Abstract - This article presents the design of a low-cost Internet of Things (IoT) system for real-time air quality monitoring with Wi-Fi connection and communication powered by *Blynk*. The desired monitoring parameters in the project include suspended particles (PM2.5) and carbon dioxide (CO₂). The results obtained demonstrate the accuracy and feasibility of the proposed solution.

Keywords: Low-cost IoT; air quality monitoring; *Blynk*; suspended particles; carbon dioxide

INTRODUCTION

Air quality is an essential factor for public health and environmental well-being [1]. With increased industrial and urban activities, continuously monitoring atmospheric pollutants has become an urgent demand [2]. These pollutants, such as suspended particles (PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), and carbon monoxide (CO), are known to cause a range of health issues, from respiratory diseases to cardiovascular complications.

Improving air quality is a worldwide demand. Specifically in Brazil, low air humidity in the rainless period, considerably increases the risk of fire, further compromising air quality in cities near the agricultural and forest regions [3].

In this context, technology has played a crucial role in developing devices and sensors capable of measuring and monitoring air quality in real time [4] [5]. The use of accurate and low-cost sensors allows not only large-scale monitoring but also the creation of smart solutions to mitigate the effects of air pollution.

This work presents the development of an air quality measuring system named AirGuard by the team. The system integrates microcontroller with sensors that measure of multiple air quality parameters, providing real-time data that can be used for detailed analyses and decision-making. Additionally, the project aims to combine technical precision with economic accessibility, making the technology feasible for applications in various environments, from urban areas to rural communities.

DEVELOPMENT

The proposed Project uses a 32-bit NodeMCU microcontroller, with 80 to 160 MHz clock, and a standard 802.11b/g/n connection of 2.4 GHz already shipped on the same module. Figure 1 presents the NodeMCU pin diagram [6].

Figure 1 – NodeMCU pin diagram.
Source: Adapted of [6]

The NodeMCU ESP8266 was applied as the project controller, collecting information from the DSM501A and DHT22 sensors and sending this data to the *Blynk* platform. *Blynk* is an IoT platform that allows you to control electronic devices remotely using a smartphone. It provides a panel by which the user can access the graphical interface using different widgets. In addition, *Blynk* can store and display sensor data. Another facility of *Blynk* is that it has libraries for the NodeMCU ESP8266, making it easier for this project to design [6]. The DHT22 sensor was used to obtain the local temperature and humidity and transmit it to the controller. Meanwhile, the DSM501A is a dust sensor module used to obtain the PM_{2.5} concentration. This measurement was carried out by counting the low PWM pulses that the controller received for 30 seconds (as per the manufacturer's instructions [7]) to perform the calculation.

Figure 2 presents the circuit of the system developed, with its components listed in Table 1.

Figure 2 – Internal Circuit of the System.

TABLE 1 – Components Used in the Project.

Item	Quantity
NODEMCU ESP8266	1
DSM501A	1
DHT22	1
DISPLAY LCD 16X2 I2C	1

The air quality PM 2.5 concentration has the range presented on Table 2.

TABLE 2 – Air Quality PM 2.5 concentrations.

Concentration (C)	Air Quality
$C < 1,000$	Clean (“Ar: Excelente”)
$1,000 < C < 10,000$	Good (“Ar: Bom”)
$10,000 < C < 20,000$	Moderate (“Ar: Razoável”)
$20,000 < C < 50,000$	Unhealthy (“Ar: Insalubre”)
$C > 50,000$	Hazard (“Ar: Perigoso”)

If umity is below 30% the system also display a message on the visor and *Blynk* user interface.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The air quality measurement system demonstrated satisfactory performance during tests conducted at room temperature, with the DSM501A sensor showing a good capacity for detecting PM2.5 particles. The combination of the DSM501A with the DHT22 sensor, which provided consistent humidity measurements, enabled a comprehensive analysis of air conditions. Figure 3 shows the final assembly of the AirGuard.

Figure 4 shows the results of a test of environment with bad quality air, with a message displayed on the system’s screen – “AIR: unhealthy” (“AR: insalubre” – PORTUGUESE).

Figure 3 – IoT air quality measurement system in a box.

Figure 4 – Result of a test conducted in an unhealthy air.

Figure 5 presents the result of another test, showing the user interface visualization through the *Blynk* platform. As can be observed, the system presents graphic and numeric shape measurements of the amount of air-suspended particles (PM2.5) in green, temperature in degrees in red (“Temperatura” - PORTUGUESE), and relative humidity of air in blue (“Umidade” - PORTUGUESE).

The results validate the suitability of the sensors used. The integration of the device with the *Blynk* platform was successful, facilitating real-time remote monitoring through mobile devices.

The system developed not only meets the technical requirements for measurement and monitoring but also stands out for its internet connectivity and user-friendly interface. The goal of creating an efficient and accessible device was also achieved, as the components used demonstrated a balance between cost and performance. It is expected that the system developed can serve as a foundation for future innovations in the field of environmental monitoring, significantly contributing to the mitigation of the harmful effects of air pollution.

Figure 5 – Results on Blynk user interface.

Finally, the results obtained from this project highlight the device's efficiency, though the need for future improvements is notable. These include adding another sensor to increase the range of variables measured and incorporating a bi-color LED to visually alert users to dangerous air conditions.

CONCLUSION

The AIRGUARD system presented here achieved the objective by meeting the measurement and monitoring requirements. By providing internet connectivity and utilizing the Blynk cloud platform, the system also offered a user-friendly interface for easy understanding and interaction. The goal of creating an accessible and efficient air quality monitoring tool was a success. AIRGUARD enables real-time data visualization and remote monitoring capabilities. This integration not only enhances user engagement but also facilitates prompt decision-making based on the collected environmental data.

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